

Analysis of Network Robustness in Scale-Free Networks

Jay Shankar & Joe Kelly

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1 Abstract

Networks are ubiquitous. We live in a society that is more connected than ever before. Connected Society affects our social professional lives in several ways such as faster epidemic spreading high speed information transmission. Our connected society has resulted in development of networks of higher link density leading to the birth of scale-free networks. But how robust are these scale-free networks? Researchers and network theorists have established models to explain the properties of networks around us. Although, well known random graph models such as Erdos-Renyi & Watts Strogatz have helped us understand the basic network topology, they fall short on the understanding of degree distribution found in many real world networks, the power law distribution. Robustness in networks is crucial for its survival against node failures and establishing its resiliency and integrity. Are real-world networks which obey the properties of scale-free networks robust? We believe understanding the scale-free network topology especially the presence of large hubs will enhance network robustness. We intend to test our hypothesis about robustness of scale-free networks in the areas of biological networks, Internet and NetworkX scale-free network during the course of this project.

2 Introduction: Why should we care?

Robustness is often thought of in terms of a network's capacity to maintain functionality in the face of external attacks. Ecological networks defy extreme environmental changes. Robustness in a scale-free network is rooted in its scale-free topology[1]. Communication networks like the Internet often sustain local failure events such as malfunction, errors, and attacks, without causing catastrophic global failures. On the flip side, some small failures in for instance, a financial network can propagate to affect the whole network. Robustness can be correlated with connectivity in that connected components enables network integration. Without connected components a network may become disconnected and disintegrated. Is this true for scale-free networks as well? What will happen to the scale-free network's overall connectivity and integration if we remove some components or connections, and equally, how will this failure then spread within the network?

Scale-free networks are defined as networks, that have a degree distribution that follows a power law.[4] That is, $p(x) \propto x^{-\alpha}$ usually between 2 and 3. Clauset, Shalizi and Newman in [4] argue that networks that strictly obey a power law distribution are rare. The argument is really one of how strictly a network adheres to a power law. What we have identified in the networks we study for this paper is a significant presence of hubs, and seemingly little restriction on the size of these nodes. We believe this conforms to the understanding of scale-free networks advanced in Barabasi in [8].

3 Literature Review

It has been established in [3] that scale-free networks are quite robust to random failure because of their network topology. At random, it is most likely that an inconsequential node is removed. For this reason, we focus our attention to targeted attacks.

In [7], the authors analyze targeted attacks looking at several different theoretical and empirical networks in order to test robustness. Robustness is defined as the amount of shrink applied to the network's largest component. Removing a fraction of nodes is called percolation. Other literature such as [2][3] had tested removing elements from a network based on random chance or node degree. The innovation in [7] is to remove nodes based on more complex measures such as degree centrality, eigenvector centrality, closeness centrality and betweenness centrality. Nodes are either removed all at once or one-by-one. The paper argues "the vulnerability of the protein-protein interaction network should be modeled by sequential targeted attack." (p.9) Only one node would be removed in each generation, and then the new protein would be able to calculate, say betweenness centrality on the new network. For protein networks, it was determined that betweenness centrality was the metric most effective for network degradation. Our project will attempt to verify these results.

In chapter 8.3.1 of [8], the author discusses another way to test network robustness, the Molloy-Reed criteria. The Molloy-Reed criteria states that if

$$\frac{\langle k^2 \rangle}{\langle k \rangle} > 2$$

then the network will have a giant component. We will apply this criteria to test at what point this metric becomes less than 2. There are a number of papers that cite the Molloy-Reed paper [11]. It seems our approach of inverse percolation is unique in the literature. In [12] for instance, argues that the highest degree in the graph has a significant impact on the giant component, but the application of the Molloy-Reed paper was just as a basis for the configuration model. We will apply the Molloy-Reed criteria to the different centrality measures outlined in [7]. Unlike [5,6] which focuses on disrupting a network based on removing edges, we will focus our time on inverse percolation as described in [8], which will target node removal.

4 Problem Statement & Motivation

We wanted to measure the extent to which scale-free networks are robust under either random failure or targeted attack. Barabasi [8] looked at the size of the giant component, but also mentioned that Molloy-Reed is another method of testing robustness. What does the Molloy Reed criteria look like under inverse percolation?

5 Data

This project uses three sources of data. We used a dataset compiled by the Center for Applied Internet Data Analysis (CAIDA) which describes a network of routers connected to each other compiled.[9] In this network, the nodes are routers, and they are connected if they are directly connected via cables. Throughout the paper, this will be referred to as the Internet network.

We also tested a Drug-protein target interaction network. This network contains information on which genes (i.e., proteins encoded by genes) are targeted by drugs that are on the U.S. market. Drug targets are molecules that play a critical role in the transport, delivery or activation of the drug. Drug target information is widely used to facilitate computational drug target discovery, drug design, drug docking or screening, drug metabolism prediction, drug interaction prediction, and general pharmaceutical research. [10] Throughout the paper, this will be referred to as the Drug-protein network.

As a baseline, we computed a scale-free network using the scale-free graph function in NetworkX in Python.

6 Methods & Evaluation

There are a number of different ways to attack a network. A network can suffer random failure of nodes. We can model this scenario by randomly removing nodes from the network. Another way to attack a network would be by removing the most important node. In [3], the most important node selected for removal was based on the highest degree. In [7], several other ways of calculating the most important node to be chosen for degree were outlined. These were covered in class - Eigenvector Centrality, Betweenness, and Closeness.

There are also two different ways to attack a network. If we wanted to remove the top $x\%$ of a graph, this could be based on the initial graph only. Alternatively, after the removal of one node, we could recompute the centrality measures listed above, and then figure out the most important node to remove on the subsequent graph. Then, upon removal of this node, we would have another graph that we would compute centrality measures. This process would repeat on a graph-by-graph basis until $x\%$ of the nodes were removed. We choose to attack our networks based on all of these measures of “most important node”.

There were two critical ways that we measured the “robustness” of a network. In [8], Barabasi discusses inverse percolation – the removal of one node at a time from a network. In this discussion, the giant component is used as a proxy for robustness. In our analysis, we measure the size of the network’s giant component in subsequent graphs as a percentage of the size of the giant

Figure 1: Attack tolerance with random removal and targeted removal

component in the initial graph. We determine a critical value of 1% of the size of the giant component.

The other way we decided to determine the robustness of the network was by computing the Molloy-Reed statistic on subsequent graphs. We use a critical value of 2, as outlined in [8].

7 Results & Discussion

We found that the Drug-protein, Internet and NetworkX Scale-free network were quite robust under random failure mode. It would take roughly 92% of the nodes to be removed at random in order to disrupt the giant component to less than 1% of its original size. Figure 1 illustrates that the results are consistent across the three networks, with the solid lines. On the other hand, we found that targeted attacks based on randomness tend to disrupt the giant component quickly. Between about 10-15% of the nodes need to be removed to fully disrupt the network. It appears that the NetworkX scale-free network is the most robust under random attack, and the weakest under targeted attack. This inverse relationship makes sense. If the NetworkX scale-free network had fewer, but more critical, nodes, then it would be more vulnerable to targeted attack. And similarly, it would be less likely to hit the few critical nodes if the nodes failed at random. These findings are consistent with [8].

Figure 2: Centrality measures with recalculation, Drug-protein Network

Next, we looked at what would happen if we targeted nodes based on other centrality measures. First we look at the scenario where we recalculate the centrality measure and determine the most important node on subsequent graphs. Figure 2 looks at the real-world Drug-Protein network for inverse percolation. Random failure on this graph again demonstrates robustness. On this graph, we also see how the different centrality measures perform. The most effective attack is betweenness, followed by closeness. That is, if a researcher wants to attack and disrupt a network, these would be the best option. Only about 4% of the nodes would need to be removed. The Drug-protein network is slightly more robust against an attack based on degree or Eigenvector. In that case, about 7% would need to be removed.

Figure 3 looks at the hypothetical NetworkX scale-free network. Here, all of the various centrality measures perform roughly the same. After removing about 5% of the nodes by any measure, the giant component is disrupted. This is interesting, because the choice of centrality measure made a difference in our real world graph, but not in the scale-free network. Additionally, there is some differentiation in terms of the exact percentage of nodes that must be removed between the two graphs.

Figure 3: Centrality measures with recalculation, Scale-Free

Recalculation would be the method of attack that would make most sense for the Drug-protein network. A scientist could remove one node, and then a new generation of cells would reproduce without the node, after which a scientist could target the next most important node and so on.

If an attack does not lend itself to recalculation or if attackers are not savvy enough to perform recalculation, another scenario presents itself – an attack based on the initial graph only. In this scenario, Degree and Betweenness removal are the most effective attacks at disrupting the network. That is, the degree information, and values for Betweenness centrality are rather good predictors of which nodes to remove. The slope for either chart is quite steep for the first about 10% of nodes removed, and after that point the information contained on the initial graph is not as good at predicting the true nodes that will most disrupt the network. Using a no-recalculation approach, degree attacks are the most effective at disrupting the network – about 15% of the nodes should be removed to meet our critical threshold for giant component analysis. The Drug-protein network is most robust against an Eigenvector attack, with about 60% of the nodes required to be removed before the Giant Component drops below 1% of its original size.

Figure 4: Drug-protein Network inverse percolation with recalculation off

For comparison purposes, we ran the same analysis on the NetworkX Scale-Free Network. While the graph of course is different, we see consistency in terms of the attacks that a network is most vulnerable to, and attacks that a network is most robust against. The Scale-Free graph is most vulnerable to Degree and Betweenness attacks, and most robust against Eigenvector and Closeness attacks.

Figure 5: NetworkX scale-free inverse percolation with recalculation off

Lastly, we looked at how inverse percolation impacted the Molloy-Reed statistic. Here, the critical point is 2. We assume the network no longer has a giant component when the threshold drops below 2. Due to computational costs, this analysis was performed only for the and the Drug-protein and NetworkX Scale-free network. Figure 6 contains the results of the various centrality measures with and without recalculation. This can be compared to Figure 3 giant component analysis with recalculation on and Figure 5 giant component analysis with recalculation off.

In all cases, we see that recalculation on performs better. Removing about 10% of the nodes is sufficient regardless of centrality measure to disrupt the network. In Figure 5, we see that more nodes need to be removed compared to Figure 3 for Giant Component failure at our 1% threshold. We don't see as significant shift for Degree and Betweenness as we would expect from Figure 5. In particular, Eigenvector removal without recalculation performs much worse than with recalculation in Figure 5. In contrast, Figure 6 shows the Molloy-Reed criteria is not affected as much. We do see that Closeness centrality appears significantly worse under no-recalculation in both Figure 5 and 6.

Ultimately, we conclude that Molloy-Reed is a different measure than great component analysis, and produces different answers regarding how robust a network is against an Eigenvector-based attack without recalculation.

Figure 6: Molloy-Reed test for NetworkX Scale-Free network

The graphs in Figure 7(c) and (d) are roughly similar to their counterparts in Figure 6. The network here is the Drug-protein network, and it is most vulnerable to a Recalculation True option. The graphs show greater resilience to Recalculation False attacks. The Drug-protein network shows an even greater resilience than the NetworkX Scale-Free network, with about 20% of nodes being required to be removed in the Drug-protein Network compared to statistics that are closer to 10% for the NetworkX Scale-Free network. This would seem to indicate that the exact structure of the network has a significant impact on these two attack methodologies. Further research would be warranted to help determine what characteristics in particular can help predict resilience.

The graphs in Figure 7(a) and (b) are quite unusual compared to their counterparts in Figure 6. The Molloy-Reed criteria is off the chart until 20% or 60% of nodes are removed respectively. We only reach the critical point at removal of 40%+ or 90%+ of the nodes are removed.

Figure 7: Molloy-Reed test for Drug-protein network

Additionally, both Drug-protein attacks demonstrate non-monotonically decreasing behavior. If inverse percolation is targeting the “most important” nodes, one would expect that the Molloy-Reed criteria would decrease at each stage. This leads us to believe that, if our calculations are correct, that the estimates of “most important” for Betweenness and Closeness under Recalculation False are quite inaccurate. The nodes that are being removed must be far from the most important around the increases in the graph. It must be that already disconnected nodes are being removed, leading to an increase in the Molloy-Reed statistic.

Again, we see inconsistency between the Giant Component analysis for Drug-protein network in Figure 4 and Molloy-Reed analysis in Figure 7. Giant component analysis shows that the networks are relatively robust with Eigenvector or Closeness attacks. In Molloy Reed analysis, Eigenvector attacks are quite effective at disrupting the network, while the network seems robust against Betweenness attacks. The threshold points are again inconsistent between Giant Component Recalculation False analysis and Molloy Reed Recalculation False analysis.

It is interesting to note that the Molloy Reed paper [11] was originally drafted in the context of Random Graphs. It may not apply to other models of graphs, which may be what we are seeing here. It would be interesting to repeat our investigation on random graphs.

8 Conclusion

Regardless of any inconsistencies between metrics, our conclusions about network robustness are overall consistent with [6] and [7]. Scale-free Networks are robust against random attack, and vulnerable to targeted attack. Choosing different methods for attacking a network can have a significant impact on how vulnerable a network is to an attack. Molloy-Reed provides different answers than giant component analysis. In either case, networks are most vulnerable to recalculation true attacks.

Any process that relies on random removal of nodes would be generally robust in a scale-free network. Disruptions to contagion, whether simple like disease or virus, or complex like ideas would be robust under a random attack, but vulnerable under a targeted attack.

Further, specific analysis of contagion may be interesting. One research question may be, “given a fixed threshold and number of exposures, how does inverse percolation impact the number of nodes influenced by social reinforcement?”

9 References

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